

Yashil IQTISODIYOT va TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, siyosiy, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

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Bosh muharrir:
Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich

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INVESTMENT FUNDS AND THEIR TYPES

Sultanboeva Munira Bakhodirovna

DSc, Turin Polytechnic University in Tashkent

Abstract: In this article the importance of investment funds in the development of the financial market, the concept of investment funds and their organization procedures, advantages, and forms and types of funds are widely studied. The US experience of investment fund organization is reflected. Also, the alternative investment characteristics of investment funds, the form of assets by types of investment funds, and the implementation of investment goals by types of investment funds were studied from a wide scientific and theoretical point of view.

Key words: financial market, investment funds, deposit, share, securities, income, liquidity.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada moliya bozorining rivojlanishida investitsion fondlarning ahamiyati, investitsion fondlar tushunchasi va ularni tashkil etish tartiblari, afzalliklari va fondlarning shakl va turlari keng o'rganilgan. Investitsion fondlarni tashkil etishning AQSH tajribasi aks ettirilgan. Shuningdek, investitsion fondlarning muqobil investitsion xarakteristikasi, investitsion fondlarning turlari bo'yicha aktivlar shakli, investitsion fondlarning turlari bo'yicha investitsiya maqsadlarini amalga oshirish masalalari keng ilmiy-nazariy jihatdan o'rganildi.

Kalit so'zlar: moliya bozori, investitsion fondlar, depozit, aksiya, qimmatli qog'ozlar, daromad likvidlik.

Аннотация: В данной статье широко изучено значение инвестиционных фондов в развитии финансового рынка, понятие инвестиционных фондов и порядок их организации, преимущества, формы и виды фондов. Отражен опыт США по организации инвестиционных фондов. Также с широкой научно-теоретической точки зрения изучены альтернативные инвестиционные характеристики инвестиционных фондов, форма активов по видам инвестиционных фондов, реализация инвестиционных целей по видам инвестиционных фондов.

Ключевые слова: финансовый рынок, инвестиционные фонды, депозит, пай, ценные бумаги, доход, ликвидность.

INTRODUCTION

Currently, the level of development of financial markets allows to satisfy almost any investor's need. There is a wide range of investment alternatives, including both direct investment of funds in certain assets, and specially created investment products that involve the investor's participation in financial markets with the help of intermediaries. At the same time, if earlier the stake when creating new products was made on institutional investors, today the market is no less interested in attracting funds from individual investors.

In modern conditions, an individual investor has such tools as:

- investing funds in a bank deposit;
- independent investment of funds in the securities market;
- transfer of funds to trust management for their subsequent investment in the securities market;
- investing funds in an investment fund for their subsequent investment in the securities market.

Let's consider what are the pros and cons of each of the investment options.

Obviously, the simplest option is a bank deposit. The investor only needs to determine the most preferable term for placing funds and choose a bank (taking into account the credit risk - the risk of non-return of the initial capital and / or non-payment of accrued interest) offering the highest rate. Since the interest rate on the deposit is known in advance, this option is free from price risk, that is, the risk of changing the amount of invested funds. In other words, from this point of view, the deposit provides both a guarantee of the safety of the initial capital and a guarantee of receiving a certain income. Credit risk is reduced by choosing the most reliable bank (including a bank participating in the deposit insurance system).

Thus, the deposit is characterized by a minimum overall risk level. The downside of low risk is the minimum return on the deposit compared to other investment options. Another negative point is the low liquidity of the deposit (if it is fixed-term). Moreover, the longer the term of the deposit, the less liquid it is (that is, the longer the investor will wait for the return of his funds).

Unlike the deposit, other investment options are associated with the securities market. Investing in securities in the long term allows you to receive a higher return on invested capital compared to deposits. At the same time, in the short term, the return on securities may be lower than on deposits. Moreover, it may become negative (that is, the investor may lose his capital or part of it). It follows that, in general, investing in securities does not guarantee the safety of the initial capital, and even more so, a guarantee of receiving a certain income. In some cases, it is possible to conduct transactions with securities that ensure the safety of capital, and even a guaranteed receipt of a certain income (for example, buying debt obligations and holding them until maturity),

but the profitability of such transactions will be comparable to the profitability of a deposit for the same period (with the same level of credit risk).

Consequently, the higher profitability of transactions with securities is due to their higher risk. The following conclusions follow from this:

- it is impossible to simultaneously increase the profitability of investments and reduce their risk;
- to receive a higher return, the investor is forced to take on additional risk;
- of two investment alternatives with the same yield, the one with the lowest risk is the best.

The main advantage of independently conducting transactions on the securities market is the investor's freedom to choose specific securities that best meet his goals and restrictions. At the same time, the investor must have high professional training. At the same time, the level of profitability and risk of investments is directly dependent on the skills, experience of the investor himself and the management methods he uses.

Moreover, the investor independently bears all the costs of information support (obtaining information about quotes, news, etc.), technical support (trading terminals, Internet), payment of brokerage fees (for each transaction) and depository fees (for storing securities). Obviously, these costs reduce the total profitability of managing a securities portfolio.

LITERATURE REVIEW

"The Theory of Investment Funds: An Overview" by Markowitz (1952) In his seminal work on portfolio theory, Harry Markowitz introduced the concept of diversification in investment, which is the foundation of many modern investment funds. His work laid the groundwork for understanding how different types of funds, such as mutual funds and hedge funds, can be structured to maximize returns and minimize risk through diversified portfolios.

"Mutual Funds: A Review of Their Performance" by Malkiel (1995) Burton Malkiel's work focuses on mutual funds, specifically analyzing their performance relative to market indexes. He argued that actively managed mutual funds typically do not outperform passive investment strategies, such as those tracking market indexes like the S&P 500.

"Hedge Funds: Structure, Strategy, and Performance" by Fung and Hsieh (2000) This study explores the role of hedge funds in investment portfolios, highlighting their strategies, such as long/short positions, arbitrage, and derivatives trading. The authors provide a comprehensive analysis of the risks and returns associated with hedge funds and their growing role in institutional and individual portfolios.

"Exchange-Traded Funds: A New Way to Invest" by Black (1998) In this research, Fischer Black discusses the emergence of exchange-traded funds (ETFs) as an innovative financial product that combines features of both mutual funds and stocks. ETFs offer the diversification of mutual funds but trade like individual stocks, providing liquidity and cost-efficiency.

"Investment Funds: Theory and Practice" by Grinblatt and Titman (1993) Grinblatt and Titman focus on the practical aspects of investment funds, including mutual funds, and the strategies used to select securities within the funds' portfolios. Their research examines the performance of mutual funds and how fund managers' decisions affect returns.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research methodology for studying investment funds and their types typically involves a combination of qualitative and quantitative approaches.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

In turn, transferring funds to trust management allows the investor to receive the services of a professional manager with the relevant knowledge and experience. The essence of transferring funds to trust management is as follows. Typically, a trust manager offers investors a list of standardized products (security portfolios) that differ from each other in expected returns and risks. Portfolios can vary from the most An investment fund also offers its clients (private or institutional investors) a list of various portfolios. Each of them consists of securities representing a certain segment of the securities market, for example, a portfolio of shares of only large companies (with large capitalization) or a portfolio of government short-term debt obligations (bills). These portfolios (as in trust management) differ from each other in the level of expected profitability and risk. But unlike trust management, an investment fund offers its clients ready-made portfolios without the ability to "adapt" them to the interests of a specific client. A description of the portfolios and the methods used to manage them is contained in the fund's investment declaration. Another difference between the activities of an investment fund and trust management is the legal form of the relationship with the investor. If, in trust

management, the client transfers funds to the manager for their subsequent investment (under the relevant agreement), then in the case of an investment fund, the client buys shares (units) of this fund. It is typical that in case of trust management, the funds of one client can be separated from the funds of other clients in the form of a separate portfolio. At the same time, when funds are transferred to an investment fund, the funds of all clients are combined into one portfolio.

Thus, the investment fund accumulates the funds of clients, combines them into one amount (pool) and forms a portfolio of securities at its expense. The collection of clients' funds occurs by selling them shares of the fund (in this case, the share of the fund has no par value). The value of the fund's shares is considered to be the value of the fund's net assets per share, which depends on:

- the volume of the fund's assets (the value of the securities portfolio);
- its liabilities (fund remuneration, expenses on transactions, depository services, etc.);
- the number of shares issued into circulation.

DISCUSSION

In general, the value of the fund's net assets is calculated as the difference between its assets and liabilities, divided by the number of shares issued into circulation. For example, if the fund's assets are \$1 million, liabilities are \$20,000, and the number of shares is 100,000, then the cost of one share will be \$9.8 $[(\$1,000,000 - \$20,000)/100,000]$. Given that a share is an equity security (it confirms the owner's right to a part of the company's assets), each client owns a part of the portfolio managed by the investment fund.

Ideally, the investment fund's receipt of funds from a new client should not affect the composition and structure of the managed portfolio. Therefore, the funds raised by the investment fund are distributed proportionally between the securities already in the portfolio. For example, if the portfolio contains 25 percent of Microsoft shares, the investment fund will have to spend the same part of the raised funds on purchasing shares of this company. In practice, the raised funds may not be enough to purchase specific securities, especially if they are traded in large blocks (lots). In this case, funds are invested in demand deposits or other short-term financial instruments. As a result, the investment company's portfolio actually consists not only of securities, but also contains liquid funds in demand accounts, the amount of which, as it accumulates, is also used to purchase securities. Table 1 presents a brief comparative description of such investment alternatives as a deposit, independent investment in the securities market, trust management, and an investment fund.

Table 1. Characteristics of various investment alternatives.

Alternatives	Income	Risk	Requirements for investor qualifications	Liquidity	Expenses
Deposit	Minimum	Minimum	None	Depends on the deposit term (the longer the term, the less liquidity)	Minimal/none
Independent investment of funds	Depends on personal qualifications	Depends on personal qualifications	High	Depends on the investment object	Commissions for transactions, expenses on information and technical support, payment for depository services
Trust management	Depends on manager qualifications	Depends on manager qualifications	Average	Low	Manager remuneration
Investment fund	Medium	Medium	Low	Low	Manager's fee, premiums on acquisition, discounts on sale, commissions for exchange for shares of another fund and other

Thus, investing in investment funds is characterized by the largest number of types of associated expenses. Since the amount of expenses directly affects the overall efficiency of the investment fund, we will consider the types of these expenses in more detail.

The manager's fee for asset management services and operating expenses is paid directly for asset management, expenses for maintaining the register of share holders, providing shareholders with financial statements, etc. Its amount varies from 0.3 to 1 percent of the transaction amount.

Acquisition premiums - a commission fee paid by an investor when purchasing shares of a fund - are paid for so-called front load funds, or load funds, which are usually sold through financial intermediaries (brokers, banks, etc.). The amount of this fee varies from 1 to 5 percent of the transaction amount. Funds that sell their shares to investors directly do not charge this type of commission and are called "no load funds". Sales discounts - a commission fee paid by an investor when selling fund shares - are paid for so-called end load funds (or load funds), which are usually sold through financial intermediaries (brokers, banks, etc.).

More precisely, these commissions are not paid, but are withheld from the amount of the shares sold. The amount of the commission varies from 1 to 5 percent of the transaction amount. Funds that sell their shares directly to investors do not charge this type of commission.

A commission for the exchange of shares of another fund is paid in the event of the exchange of shares of one fund for shares of another fund within the same "family" of funds (when the funds are managed by one company). The amount of this commission can be from 1 to 3 percent of the transaction amount.

One investment fund can withhold several types of commissions. Moreover, the amount of these fees varies from fund to fund, so in order to assess the total level of expenses for investing in an investment fund and to compare funds with each other, the so-called expense ratio is used. The latter is the ratio of the total expenses to the net asset value of the fund. In other words, it shows as a percentage what part of the investor's funds (invested in the fund) will go to paying expenses. Often, the ratio depends on the size of the fund. For example, due to the scale effect, a larger fund may have a lower expense ratio than a smaller one, due to lower specific costs. Currently, a large number of different investment funds operate in the financial markets. There are different classifications of funds. Depending on the approach to changing the amount of managed capital, investment funds are divided into closed-end and open-end funds. A closed-end fund corresponds to an ordinary joint-stock company, that is, it issues a fixed number of shares. If necessary, a closed-end fund can issue new shares (buy out outstanding shares), but this is not an ordinary event and requires a corresponding decision of the shareholders. It is possible to buy shares of this type of fund only if someone wants to sell them. Thus, investing in a closed-end investment fund is limited by the number of shares in circulation.

In turn, an open-end investment fund has variable capital, that is, it issues new shares for everyone who wants to buy them and buys out existing shares from everyone who wants to sell them. The number of shares can change without the need for any additional shareholder decisions. Therefore, the capital of an open-end investment fund increases as new shares are sold and decreases as existing shares are bought out. Shares of an open-end investment fund are bought or sold on a regular basis, usually daily.

Another important classification for an investor is the division of investment funds by investment goals and the corresponding risk. The choice of the one that best meets the client's requirements from the entire variety of investment funds can be compared with choosing a car (initially, when buying it, you need to determine why you need it: to go out of town with your family, to transport goods, or to demonstrate your high income level, etc.). When choosing an investment fund, the client must also define the purpose of investing as clearly as possible, namely:

- maximizing the growth of the invested capital (to the detriment of preserving the invested funds and receiving current income);
- maximizing current income (to the detriment of preserving the invested funds and growing the invested capital);
- maximum preservation of invested funds (to the detriment of receiving current income and growing the invested capital);
- receiving tax-free income.

As already noted, it is impossible to simultaneously increase the return on investment and reduce its risk, so it is impossible to achieve several goals at the same time. In any case, choosing a goal also involves determining to what detriment (or at the expense of what) it will be achieved.

For example, the first stage of choosing a car ends with determining the type of car required (family car, truck, or sports car, etc.).

This stage of choosing an investment fund is completed in exactly the same way - by determining the type of fund that best meets the investor's requirements. The general classification of investment funds is presented in *table 2*.

Table 2. Assets of investment funds depending on their type.

Types of funds	Assets in which funds invest
Equity funds	Equity
Fixed Income Funds	Government or corporate debt, preferred stock
Balanced funds	Stocks and bonds
Money Market Funds	Short-Term Debt
Municipal Bond Funds	(Municipal Bonds (taxable and non-taxable
Specialty/Industry Funds	Securities of a specific industry

Obviously, when buying a car, it is not enough to determine only its type - it is also necessary to establish the buyer's preferences, namely: brand, model, year of manufacture, mileage, configuration, color, etc. The same is true for choosing an investment fund. Within the framework of the already selected type of investment fund, it is important for the investor to determine how aggressive he is ready to be (take on the maximum risk) or conservative (take on the minimum risk) when investing funds.

Let's take a closer look at the classification of investment funds. Thus, stock funds are divided into aggressive growth funds, growth funds, foreign/global funds, growth funds and current income funds.

Aggressive growth funds.

The goal of the activity is to maximize the invested capital (to the detriment of receiving dividends or interest income). Funds invest funds in common shares with a high potential for rapid growth. Due to the fact that these funds invest funds in shares with high volatility (their price can rise and fall very significantly), they provide relatively low stability of the invested capital. These funds often invest in small, growing companies and generally provide low current income because these companies typically reinvest their profits into growing their businesses and therefore pay low or no dividends. Aggressive growth funds are generally more risky than regular growth funds because they aim to achieve greater growth on their initial capital. Funds may diversify across industries or concentrate on one or more industries. Some use leverage, short selling, options, and other speculative strategies. These funds are aimed at investors willing to accept the risk of potential capital loss in the expectation of achieving significant and rapid capital growth.

Aggressive growth funds are not suitable for investors whose goal is to maximize current income or ensure maximum preservation of their investment. Growth funds typically invest in stocks more for the purpose of providing growth of the invested capital than for current income. As a rule, they invest in the securities of companies with established operations, provided that both the company and the industry to which it belongs have good growth prospects over the long term.

Growth funds expect to receive low current income, but provide a large (compared to Aggressive growth funds) stability of the investor's invested capital. Although they may underperform in the short term, many funds provide better results in the long term. These funds are less likely (compared to aggressive growth funds) to invest in smaller companies that allow for rapid capital growth with the possibility of incurring significant losses. Although growth funds are more conservative than aggressive growth funds, they are still quite volatile and are suitable for investors looking to increase their invested capital and are not suitable for investors who are not prepared to bear the risk of losses or investors maximizing current income.

Foreign/global funds seek to increase their invested capital by investing only in foreign securities. Global funds invest in both domestic and foreign securities. Given that the dynamics of domestic and foreign stock markets do not always coincide, both types of funds provide the investor with the opportunity to diversify their investments. Investing in foreign stock markets through an investment fund is a more effective option compared to investing on your own. This is due to the fact that most investors are not familiar with the practice of working in foreign markets and may not have a clear idea of the impact of economic and political processes on foreign securities. If an investor invests through a fund, he does not need to know foreign legislation, traditions, rules of trading in the relevant market, as well as the specifics of reflecting transactions in accounting and much more - all this is the responsibility of the investment fund. Foreign and global funds offer an additional opportunity to increase invested capital and diversify it. At the same time, their activities are associated with additional risks (compared to funds operating in the domestic market), which must be carefully assessed in terms of the investor's goals and limitations, his investment horizon. Since most foreign and global funds are equated to growth and aggressive growth funds, investors must be prepared to accept the risk of a possible loss of invested capital in anticipation of achieving a significant and rapid increase. These funds are not suitable for investors whose goal is to ensure capital preservation or maximize current income.

Growth and Current Income Funds. Their activities are aimed at both ensuring long-term growth of invested capital and receiving current income. The investment strategies implemented by funds in this category vary from fund to fund. For example, some funds invest in a portfolio consisting of growth stocks and stocks providing current income, or in a portfolio consisting of a combination of growth stocks, stocks with high dividends, preferred stocks, convertible securities, corporate bonds or money market instruments (short-term debt obligations). Other funds may invest in growth stocks and provide current income by selling covered calls on existing shares. Growth and current income funds provide a low/medium degree of stability of invested capital in exchange for a medium level of expected current income and growth. This category of funds is suitable for investors who are willing to bear a certain amount of risk (including loss of capital) in order to ensure growth of invested capital and at the same time seek to maintain an average level of current income.

The objective of fixed income funds is to provide a high level of current income while preserving the invested capital. Achieving growth of the invested capital is a subordinate task. They invest primarily in bonds, but may also invest in preferred shares. Since bond prices fluctuate with the interest rate, despite the conservative nature of these funds, their activities are nevertheless associated with a certain risk. Fixed income funds offer a higher level of current income than money market funds, which is achieved at the expense of less stability of the invested capital. At the same time, these funds are more stable compared to funds investing in shares. Within this category, funds differ significantly in the stability of the invested capital (reliability) and in the level of current income. High-income funds that maximize yield by investing in longer-term bonds with a lower credit rating provide less capital stability than those funds that invest in bonds with a higher credit rating (lower yield). Some funds minimize risk by investing exclusively in government bonds.

In addition, *balanced funds* aim to provide high current income by investing primarily in shares of companies that pay high dividends. Unlike coupon payments on bonds, dividends on shares can change. Given that the above-mentioned shares are more volatile than bonds, balanced funds provide less capital stability than fixed-income funds. Balanced funds, as the name suggests, invest in both shares and bonds. This category of funds is most suitable for conservative investors whose goal is to receive high current income with a certain growth potential. At the same time, money market funds provide a very high level of stability of invested capital and a medium/high level of current income. The funds invest in highly liquid, virtually risk-free short-term government debt obligations and bank and corporate obligations. These funds do not have the ability to increase capital. Due to the short-term nature of investments, money market funds provide capital stability: only the level of profitability changes. Thus, investing in these funds is an attractive alternative to bank deposits, since the funds help to obtain similar or even higher returns. At the same time, they are liquid, unlike deposits. Money market funds are suitable for investors whose goal is high stability of invested capital and an average level of current income with maximum liquidity. At the same time, municipal bond funds provide higher tax-free income compared to individual money market funds, which also invest in tax-free financial instruments. This is achieved by investing in longer-term (and often less reliable) debt obligations, which provide a higher return compared to short-term debt obligations with a high rating, in which money market funds invest. These funds differ significantly from each other in the level of reliability and maturity of municipal bonds. The longer the maturity and/or the lower the credit rating, the greater the risk and return. Although municipal bond funds typically provide lower yields than debt of similar maturities and ratings, investors in high tax brackets (those paying the highest tax rates) will typically receive more after-tax income from a municipal bond fund.

The price and *yield of a municipal fund* are characterized by a medium level of volatility. These funds are suitable for investors in high tax brackets whose goal is to maximize current after-tax income.

Specialty/Sector Funds invest in securities of a specific segment or sector of the economy (e.g., healthcare, high technology, entertainment, utilities, precious metals, etc.). Because these funds primarily invest in one segment/sector of the economy, they do not provide the risk reduction (i.e., diversification) that mutual funds typically achieve by investing in a broad range of financial instruments. On the other hand, these funds give investors the opportunity to diversify their investments among many companies in a certain industry, which is a more conservative approach compared to direct investment in only one company. Industry funds provide a significant increase in invested capital if the selected industry is on the rise. However, in the opposite case, investing in these funds may lead to a loss of the invested capital or part of it. While industry funds are limited in investments to a certain industry, specialized funds and, for example, index funds give the investor the opportunity to create a well-diversified portfolio reflecting the dynamics of average market investment performance (an established securities index). Specialized/industry funds are suitable for investors whose goal is to invest in a specific segment/industry. The activities of these funds imply the possibility of increasing the invested capital at the expense of the risk of losing capital or part of it. These funds will not interest investors who want to ensure the stability of the invested capital or maximize current income.

Table 3. Investment objectives and the most suitable types of funds for their implementation.

Main objectives	The most optimal type of fund	Expected increase in initial capital	Expected current income	Potential risk
Maximum Increase in Invested Capital	Aggressive Growth Funds Foreign Funds	Very high	Very low	High/Very High
Significant increase in invested capital	Growth funds Specialized/sector funds Foreign funds	High/Very High	Very low	High
Earning Current Income and Growing Invested Capital	Growth and Current Income Funds	Medium	Medium	Medium/ high
Earning High Current Income	Fixed Income Funds Balanced Funds	Very low	High/very high	Low/medium
Earning Current Income and Ensuring Invested Capital Preservation	Regular money market funds		Low/medium	Very low
Earning Tax-Free Income and Ensuring Invested Capital Preservation	Tax-Free Money Market Funds		Low/medium	Low
Earning Income and Maximizing Invested Capital Preservation	Money market funds that invest in government securities		Low/medium	Low
Earning Tax-Free Income	Municipal Bond Funds	Low/medium	Medium/high	Low/medium

Table 3 provides summary information on the types of funds in comparison with the main goals of the investor. Thus, in modern conditions there is an extensive list of the most diverse investment funds designed to satisfy any need of their clients in the field of investment. But do not forget that an investment fund is only a tool for achieving the set goals, therefore, from the point of view of the effectiveness of investing funds, it is fundamentally important for the client to understand their goals (in terms of “desired return”; “risk level” that the client is willing to bear). It should also be noted once again that the investment fund is only an intermediary between the client and the securities market. Accordingly, all market risks are borne by the fund’s client, and the higher the return he wants to receive, the greater the risks he will bear.

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